

Controlled Photocatalytic Deposition of ZnO Nanoparticles on 2 Poly(3-octylthiophene) Nanofibers: A Versatile Approach To Obtain 3 Organic/Inorganic Hybrid Semiconductor Assemblies

A. Balogh, B. Szabo, V. Kozma, C. Szigeti, and C. Gergely

KFKI Atomic Energy Research Institute, Budapest, H-1525, Hungary; Department of Applied and Environmental Chemistry, University of Szeged, Reirrich Square 1, Szeged, H-6720, Hungary

6 ABSTRACT: To efficiently harness the possible synergies, stemming from 8 the combination of organic conducting polymers and inorganic semi9 conductors, sophisticated assembling methods are required to control the
10 composition and morphology at the nanoscale. In this proof-of-concept
11 study, we demonstrate the in situ photocatalytic deposition of CdS
12 nanoparticles on poly(3-hexylthiophene) (P3HT) nanofibers, exploiting the 13 semiconducting nature of this polymer. The formation of the hybrid 14 assembly was monitored by UV–vis and Raman spectroscopy, Energy15 dispersive X-ray microanalysis, and X-ray powder diffraction (XRD). 16 Transmission electron microscopic studies and AFM images confirmed that 17 both the particle size and the loading can be tuned by the deposition time. 18 Photoelectrochemical studies revealed the facile transfer of photogenerated 19 electrons from P3HT to CdS, as well as that of the holes from CdS to 20 P3HT. It is believed that ensuring intimate contact between the
21 components in these nanohybrids will open new avenues in various application schemes, e.g., solar energy conversion.

Scheme 1. Illustration of the Photocatalytic Synthesis of P3HT/CdS

76 Mechanistic investigations in prior studies proved that the

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77 atomic route ($M^{2+} + 2e^- \rightarrow M$; $M + S \rightarrow MS$) is dominantly 78
responsible for the compound formation.²¹ It has also been 79
shown that the conduction band edge position of the 80
photoexcited SC particle (TiO_2 in these studies), together 81
with the reduction potential of the metal cation determines the
82 feasibility, as well as the rate of the photodeposition reaction
83 (i.e., the larger the difference the faster the reaction).¹⁵
84 In this article, we demonstrate a simple and versatile method,
85 exploiting the intrinsic semiconducting nature of CPs to 86
photodeposit metal-chalcogenide nanoparticles on their sur⁸⁷
face under visible light irradiation. The photocatalytic behavior
88 of CPs has already been demonstrated and utilized in organic
89 synthesis,²² dye-degradation,²³ as well as noble-metal
deposi⁹⁰ tion.^{24,25} In the presented study we exploit the
photoelectrons ⁹¹ generated in P3HT nanofibers to reduce Cd^{2+}
ions, in the ⁹² presence of elemental S, thus CdS nanoparticles
are formed ⁹³ (Scheme 1). Our choice on the P3HT/CdS as a
model system ⁹⁴ was deliberate, because we wanted to
demonstrate the ⁹⁵ feasibility of this approach on a composite,
which may have
⁹⁶ practical significance. Composites of poly(3-
alkylthiophenes)
⁹⁷ and metal-chalcogenides are considered
as benchmark
⁹⁸ materials of organic/inorganic hybrid solar cells.^{26,27}
⁹⁹ One-dimensional nanostructures of CPs have attracted ¹⁰⁰
significant attention recently,²⁸ because of their enhanced ¹⁰¹
electronic properties compared to their bulk counterparts. For ¹⁰²
example, self-assembled highly crystalline nanofibers of P3HT ¹⁰³
showed a 6-fold improvement in the electrical conductivity, ¹⁰⁴
rooted in the enhanced charge carrier mobility.^{29,30} Such ¹⁰⁵
beneficial features were exploited even in hybrid configu¹⁰⁶
rations;³¹ for example, P3HT nanofibers were decorated with ¹⁰⁷
 $CdSe$ ³² and CdS ³³ (via a sophisticated chemical grafting ¹⁰⁸
procedure) and showed promising performance in solar cell
¹⁰⁹ studies.

110 ■ EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

111 Materials. All chemicals used were of analytical grade. 3112
Hexylthiophene ($\geq 99\%$), lithium perchlorate ($\geq 98\%$) and 1113 absolute
ethanol were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, L1114 ascorbic acid,
cadmium nitrate tetrahydrate, and sulfur from

chloroform, and anisole from VWR International. Water 116
content of both anisole and chloroform was kept below 50 117
ppm (monitored by coulometric Karl Fischer titration) by 118
storing it over 3A zeolites. 119

Preparation Methods. Poly(3-hexylthiophene) (P3HT) ¹²⁰ was
prepared by oxidative chemical polymerization. Chloro- ¹²¹
form-based solutions of 3-hexylthiophene monomer and $FeCl_3$
¹²² were prepared and mixed at final reagent concentrations of
0.1 ¹²³ and 0.25 M, respectively. The continuously stirred
reaction ¹²⁴ mixture was kept in a closed vessel on ice bath for 6
h. The ¹²⁵ formed polymer was filtered on a filter paper (12–15
 μm pore ¹²⁶ size) and washed repeatedly with absolute ethanol
to remove ¹²⁷ the traces of the oxidant. The final product was
dried in air, ¹²⁸ under an infrared lamp. ¹²⁹

The whisker method was employed to form nanofibers from
¹³⁰ the bulk polymer. As the first step, a larger molecular weight
¹³¹ fraction of P3HT was extracted with tetrahydrofuran (THF).
¹³² Subsequently, the polymer was redissolved in a 9:1 ratio ¹³³
anisole/chloroform mixture to get a final polymer concen- ¹³⁴
tration of 1.0 g dm^{-3} . Finally, the solution was warmed up to 70
¹³⁵ °C and then instantly cooled to room temperature on an ice
¹³⁶ bath. ¹³⁷

P3HT nanofiber network thin layers were formed by drop- ¹³⁸
casting the P3HT solution on indium-tin-oxide (ITO)- ¹³⁹
covered glass substrates. The P3HT loading was about 100 ¹⁴⁰
 $\mu g \text{ cm}^{-2}$. ¹⁴¹

Synthesis of P3HT/CdS Hybrids. P3HT thin layers were ¹⁴²
placed in a closed cell and immersed in an ethanol-based ¹⁴³
solution, containing the precursors of the CdS synthesis ¹⁴⁴
($[Cd^{2+}] = 1.38 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[S_8] = 1.72 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}$ ¹⁴⁵
 dm^{-3}) and ascorbic acid ($c = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), as sacrificial hole ¹⁴⁶
scavenger. The solution was degassed by bubbling N_2 through
¹⁴⁷ it for 30 min before the synthesis. Photocatalytic synthesis of
¹⁴⁸ the P3HT/CdS hybrids was then implemented by using a
Fiber ¹⁴⁹ Lite A3000 type tungsten halogen lamp (150 W
maximum ¹⁵⁰ power output), operating in the visible range,
between $\lambda =$ ¹⁵¹ 380–800 nm. After the illumination, the hybrids
were carefully ¹⁵² washed with distilled water and absolute
ethanol, to remove the ¹⁵³ adsorbed precursors on the surface.
Solution blending was also ¹⁵⁴

Figure 1. (a) Absorbance spectra recorded during the P3HT/CdS composite formation. (b) Difference spectra from part a. The inset in part b shows the Tauc-plot derived from part b, for the sample obtained by 2 h photodeposition.

Figure 2. (a) Raman spectrum. (b) XRD diffractogram of the bare P3HT nanofibers and P3HT/CdS composite (2 h synthesis). (c) EDX spectrum of a P3HT/CdS composite (2 h synthesis).

Figure 3. TEM pictures of P3HT (a) and three P3HT/CdS hybrids after 5 min (b), 15 min (c), and 30 min photodeposition (d). Particle size distribution of the CdS particles for the samples shown in parts b and c.

208 nanofibers.^{28,30} Careful comparison of the curves, however, 209 reveals a continuous absorbance increase between 300 and 550 210 nm. To visualize these changes directly, difference spectra were 211 obtained by subtracting the spectrum of P3HT recorded before 212 irradiation (Figure 1b). The gradually 213 developing difference spectrum indicates the steady formation of CdS nanoparticles. 214 The bandgap energy of the formed material was calculated 215 using a Tauc-plot (Figure 1b), and the values were in the range

of 2.5–3.0 eV. In accordance with the small but significant 216 gradual redshift of the absorption maximum (Figure 1b), a 217 monotonous decrease in the bandgap energy was observed 218 (from 3.01 (after 15 min) to 2.51 (after 120 min)). These 219 tendencies indicate that initially very small nanoparticles 220 (quantum dots) are formed, which later grow with the 221 deposition time. After 120 min, however, the bandgap of CdS 222

Figure 4. AFM images of P3HT (a), P3HT/CdS 30 min photodeposition (b), P3HT/CdS after 60 min photodeposition (c).

Figure 5. Comparison of the reduction potentials of different metal cations and the band positions of TiO₂, CdS, and P3HT.

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223 reached the value generally reported for the bulk material
 (2.5
 224 eV).^{34,35}

225 The chemical identity of the formed P3HT/CdS hybrid was
 226 confirmed by X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman-spectroscopy,²²⁷
 and energy-dispersive X-ray microanalysis (EDX). On the EDX
 228 spectrum, both Cd and S peaks were observed (Figure 2c).²²⁹
 Semiquantitative analysis estimates about 10 wt % CdS content
 230 in the hybrid obtained after 2 h. Figure 2a depicts the Raman
 231 spectra of a P3HT nanonet and a P3HT/CdS hybrid (2 h
 232 photodeposition). In the P3HT spectrum, the $C_{\alpha}-S-C_{\alpha}$

233 deformation at 684 cm^{-1} , the symmetric $C_{\alpha}-C_{\beta}$ stretching (the
 most intense peak) at 1455 cm^{-1} , together with the

235 asymmetric $C_{\alpha'}-C_{\beta'}$ stretching at 1518 cm^{-1} are characteristic
 236 for the reduced form of P3HT.³⁶ As for the hybrid material,
 the 237 most important alteration is the appearance of a new band
 at 238 303 cm^{-1} , which is distinctive for the Cd-S stretching in
 239 CdS.³⁷ In the XRD patterns presented in Figure 2b, both
 240 P3HT- and CdS-related diffractions are present. Clearly, P3HT
 241 is completely crystalline: the most intensive sharp reflection
 at 242 $2\Theta = 5.2^{\circ}$ (100), together with the two smaller one ((200)
 and 243 (300)), is attributed to the lamellar ordering of the
 polymer 244 chains, facilitated by the overlap of the aromatic
 rings (π ²⁴⁵ stacking) and the zipper-type connection of the hexyl
 side 246 chains. The appearance of CdS-related broad
 diffractions, 247 superimposed to the P3HT peaks, in the hybrid
 assembly 248 points toward the formation of a nanocrystalline
 material. The 249 diffraction pattern is consistent with the cubic
 CdS structure

registered at constant potentials (Figure 7). However, the 356
 absolute values of these photocurrents during the photo- 357
 voltammetric scans is very interesting; while the cathodic 358
 photocurrents are five times higher in the hybrid, the anodic 359
 photocurrents show a 15–20 fold improvement compared to 360
 the bare materials. This striking effect can be interpreted by the 361
 good electrical contact between the components in the hybrid 362
 material. Upon photoexcitation under cathodic polarization, 363
 CdS is able to receive photoelectrons from P3HT (the CB edge 364
 alignment favors this transition), thus boosting cathodic 365
 photocurrents by reducing the probability of recombination. 366
 As for CdS, the photogenerated holes can oxidize P3HT 367

(hawleyite), as confirmed by literature data (JCPDS no. J 10- 250
 0454). The Scherrer equation was employed to determine the 251
 average crystallite size of the CdS particles, and $d = 5.9\text{ nm}$ was
 252 obtained. The broadening of the Raman bands as well as the
 253 shift of the polymer-related diffraction peaks (in the XRD 254
 pattern) to smaller 2Θ values is an indication of the partial 255
 oxidation of P3HT during the hybrid formation (see details 256
 below, as well as in Scheme 1).²⁹ 257

Development of the morphological features of the hybrid was
 258 monitored by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and 259
 atomic force microscopy (AFM). Figure 3a–d shows the TEM 260
 images of the bare P3HT nanofiber network and three P3HT/ 261
 CdS hybrids, obtained within 5, 15, and 30 min, respectively. 262
 We note here that in the preparation of these samples, the 263
 polymer nanofibers were directly casted on the TEM grid, and 264
 the CdS nanoparticles were in situ deposited. During longer 265
 synthesis times (i.e., over 30 min) however, the copper grid 266
 corroded through its reaction with elemental sulfur present in 267
 the solution. Beyond the obvious appearance of the nanofibers, 268
 both individual CdS nanoparticles (dark spots) and some of 269
 their aggregates are seen in the case of the hybrids (Figure 3b– 270
 d). As seen in the histograms (see Figure 3e), the average size 271
 of the primary particles was 6.8, 9.3, and 9.6 nm, after 5, 15, and
 272 30 min, respectively (in agreement with the slight decrease in
 273 the bandgap, shown above). At this juncture, we emphasize 274
 again that the histograms depict the size distribution of the 275
 primary nanoparticles (because that is the factor dictating the 276

(which acts a hole-scavenger in this case); thus, much higher 368

Figure 7. Chronoamperometric photoelectrochemical measurements of a P3HT/CdS composite (2 h) at different potentials, recorded in 0.1 M $\text{LiClO}_4/\text{acetonitrile}$ solution under periodic ($t_{\text{period}} = 30$ s) visible light irradiation ($\lambda > 380$ nm).